

Likelihood ratio based authorship verification methods applied to forensic voice comparison

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Forensic Voice Comparison

Treated as an 'open-set' problem

Forensic Voice Comparison

Even though it's available in the speech signal, existing forensic voice comparison approaches don't really include lexical or grammatical information....

1

Auditory Phonetic and Acoustic (AuPhA) approach

- Typically includes analyses of: segments, formants, f0, voice quality, disfluencies
- Expert takes into account a whole collection of features to arrive at a conclusion

2

Automatic speaker recognition

- Forms models of speech samples based on acoustic features extracted from the signal.
- Lexical and grammatical information is not (sufficiently) accounted for in automatic speaker recognition systems.

Forensic Voice Comparison

Might occasionally find some acknowledgement of lexical and grammatical information in AuPhA FVC reports.

Just some examples from a few different FVC reports produced by *Soundscape Voice Evidence*

Reports written between 2019 – present.

**Soundscape
Voice Evidence**

The logo graphic consists of a thick horizontal grey bar. Below this bar are three horizontal grey bars of decreasing width, stacked vertically, resembling a stylized sound wave or a set of steps.

Soundscape Voice Evidence report examples

Like the questioned speaker, XXX frequently uses elided forms of adverbs (e.g. 'obviously', 'basically', 'actually'), the word 'so' to finish a sentence, and the phrase 'no worries'.

Both the questioned speaker and XXX use direct reported speech when retelling an event. XXX, like the questioned speaker, uses a question in order to introduce a question.

The questioned woman and XXX both use the word 'corporation' to refer to the police.

Soundscape Voice Evidence report examples

Commonalities include the use of the phrase 'I know [something] like the back of my hand', the use of 'blah blah blah' at the end of a sentence, the use of direct reported speech... the use of 'are you listening' as an attention marker, and the non-standard use of the indefinite article, e.g. ' a angel' and 'a officer'.

Both the questioned speaker and XXX use the combination 'yeah no' at a start of a response to a question, e.g. 'yeah no I'm fine', 'yeah no that sounds good'.

Authorship Verification

Authorship analysis taps into lexical and grammatical information

- Authorship Attribution – closed-set problem

- Authorship verification – open-set problem

- *Forensic Text Comparison*

Applying a Bayesian approach

- Useful framework for open-set problems (i.e., forensic voice comparison and forensic text comparison)
- Often introduced in its empirical form
- But we don't necessarily always need to think about it empirically...

Applying a Bayesian approach

Kirchhübel co-delivered a workshop at International Association for Forensic Phonetics and Acoustics (IAFPA) 2023 on applying Bayes in Forensic Voice Comparison casework.

She discussed the idea that to apply a Bayesian approach:

- you do not have to carry out mathematical calculations
- you do not have to have access to databases.

Applying a Bayesian approach

Applying the AuPhA analytical approach, a forensic speech analyst will:

- 1) Consider the likelihood of the evidence under the same-speaker hypothesis.
- 2) Consider the likelihood of the evidence under the different-speaker hypothesis.
- 3) Deliver an overall verbal expression (e.g., ‘moderately strong support for the view that it is the same speaker in both recordings’).

Applying a Bayesian approach

But that consideration of two competing hypotheses can of course also happen empirically using databases...

Applying a Bayesian approach

But that consideration of two competing hypotheses can of course also happen empirically using databases...

$$LR = \frac{p(E|H_p)}{p(E|H_d)}$$

Similarity

Typicality

Prosecution hypothesis:
Probability of the evidence occurring, given that it is the same speaker.

Defence hypothesis:
Probability of the evidence occurring, given that it is the different speaker from the population.

Performance Measure - Cllr

Log likelihood–ratio cost function (Cllr) a measure that we can view as a ‘penalty’ score.

- Assesses the quality of the likelihood ratios
- Using Cllr means that we “penalise” a system or process according to likelihood ratios assigned to the incorrect label

Sergidou et. al. (2023)

Sergidou et. al. (2023) cottoned on to the idea of applying authorship verification techniques to forensic voice comparison

Looked at how function word frequencies can contribute to forensic voice comparison.

223 Dutch-speaking male speakers

16 telephone conversations each (approx. 5-minute conversations)

- transcribed

Sergidou et. al. (2023)

Took the 50 most frequent words from a corpus of spoken Dutch

Represent the frequency of these most frequent words for each speaker in a feature vector

Used a distance metric to compute many same-speaker scores and different-speaker scores.

Achieved Cllrs consistently below 1 (often around the 0.4 - 0.6 range).

Content masking

The cat sat on the mat and the dog sat on the chair.

The * * on the * and the * * on the * .

The N V on the N and the N V on the N .

Parts of Speech tags

Burrows' Delta

Word	NORM	author 1	author 2	NORM – author 1	NORM – author 2
a					
an					
all					
also					
some					
upon					

Cosine Delta
Most frequent 3,000 words

Impostors method

- Seidman, Shachar. 2013. Authorship Verification Using the Impostors Method. In P Forner, R Navigli, D Tufis & N Ferro (eds.), CLEF 2013 Evaluation Labs and Workshop – Working Notes Papers, 23–26. Valencia, Spain.
- Koppel, Moshe & Yaron Winter. 2014. Determining if two documents are written by the same author. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 65(1). 178–187.
- Kestemont, Mike, Justin Stover, Moshe Koppel, Folgert Karsdorp & Walter Daelemans. 2016. Authenticating the writings of Julius Caesar. *Expert Systems With Applications* 63. 86–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2016.06.029>.

Impostors method

Character 4-grams

100 repetitions

50% random features

50% random impostors

score

= % of times the candidate is top 1

Potha, Nektaria & Efstathios Stamatatos. 2020. Improved algorithms for extrinsic author verification. *Knowledge and Information Systems* 62(5). 1903–1921. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-019-01408-4>.

Ranking-Based Impostors Method

The cat sat on the mat and the dog sat on the chair.

bag

set

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

B

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

character 9-grams

Jaccard coefficient

ad don't t bak av wud w wil y wen 2 4 wiv jst dnt , 4get thanx

Strugglin get babysitter at
mo. Thats **y** never replied.
Chris is goin **w** wayne x

0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

Got go fetch milly. Val cant
cope **w** her x

0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

$$J = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = \frac{\text{number of features in } A \text{ and } B}{\text{number of features in } A \text{ or } B} = 1/2 = 0.5$$

Phi coefficient

Prosecution hypothesis

Data

The West Yorkshire Regional English Database (WYRED) (Gold, 2020).

Transcribed speech data from 97 male speakers

Four speaking tasks each:

Task 1: Mock police interview

Task 2: A telephone conversation with an accomplice

Task 3: Paired conversation

Task 4: Voicemail message

Authorship Verification based on the Likelihood Ratio of Grammar Models

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λ_G
LambdaG

Provisional title of pre-print

idiolect

Overview

The `idiolect` R package is designed to provide a comprehensive suite of tools for performing comparative authorship analysis within a forensic context using the likelihood ratio framework (e.g. Ishihara 2021). The package contains a set of authorship analysis functions that take a set of texts as input and output scores that can then be calibrated into likelihood ratios. The package is dependent on [quanteda](#) (Benoit et al. 2018) for all Natural Language Processing functions.

Still in development!
A first official release soon

References

Gold, E. (2020). *WYRED - West Yorkshire Regional English Database 2016-2019*. [Data Collection]. Colchester, Essex: UK Data Service. 10.5255/UKDA-SN-854354

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Sergidou, E-K., Scheijen, N., Leegwater, J., Cambier-Langeveld, T, and Bosma, W. (2023). *Frequent-words analysis for forensic speaker comparison*. *Speech Communication*. 150. pp 1-8.